

Unlocking cybersecurity potential in civil and defence domains in Slovenia

Authors

CCIS

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Abstract

This white paper examines the cybersecurity ecosystem in Slovenia, with a focus on cooperation between civil and defence domains. Based on the Slovenian national case study developed within the COcyber project, it provides a synthesised, policy-oriented perspective.

While Slovenia has a solid regulatory and institutional foundation, its effectiveness is limited by fragmented coordination, skills shortages, and gaps in technology transfer, information sharing, and dual-use innovation.

The paper concludes that better coordination, investment, and integration of existing capabilities are essential to strengthen national cybersecurity resilience and Slovenia's role in the European ecosystem.

Keywords

Cybersecurity, Slovenia, civil–defence cooperation, technology transfer, information sharing, dual-use innovation, cybersecurity skills, public–private cooperation, digital resilience, cybersecurity policy

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Description
CCIS	The Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia, COcyber partner responsible for the National Case Study Report of Slovenia (WP4).
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team, a group of information security experts who identify, analyse and mitigate cybersecurity incidents and threats.
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team – technical team for handling cybersecurity incidents
EU	The European Union (EU) is a political and economic union of 27 European countries, designed to foster economic cooperation, promote peace, and create a single market with free movement of goods, services, and people.
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform – open-source system for structured threat intelligence exchange
NATO	NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization) is a military alliance formed in 1949, consisting of 30 member countries from Europe and North America, aimed at ensuring collective defence and security against common threats. It operates under the principle that an attack on one member is an attack on all.
NCC-SI	National Coordination Centre for Cybersecurity – Slovenian hub within the EU Cybersecurity Competence Network
R&D	Research and development
SME	Small and medium sized enterprise
SI-CERT	Slovenian Computer Emergency Response Team – national cyber incident response authority
SIGOV-CERT	Governmental Computer Emergency Response Team – handles cybersecurity within Slovenian public administration
URSIV	Government Information Security Office of the Republic of Slovenia (Urad Republike Slovenije za informacijsko varnost)

Executive Summary

As digital systems expand and interconnect, countries increasingly depend on their ability to prevent, detect, and respond to cyber threats in a coordinated and effective way. In this context, technology transfer, information sharing, and cooperation between civil and defence actors are critical enablers of resilience in order to keep digital trust and manage economic stability and national security.

This white paper draws on the Slovenian case study developed by the COcyber project. Its purpose is not to summarise the case study, but to synthesise its key insights into a coherent and policy-oriented narrative. It identifies systemic strengths, structural weaknesses, and practical gaps in the national cybersecurity ecosystem, with a particular focus on technology transfer, information sharing, and dual-use innovation.

Slovenia provides a relevant example of a country with a solid regulatory and institutional base aligned with European frameworks, but facing challenges in the implementation and coordination of existing resources. The national ecosystem includes a broad set of actors—government, industry, academia, and civil society—supported by several institutions. However, the effectiveness of this system depends on how well these elements work together in practice to ensure cybersecurity.

The importance of this topic is increasing. Cyber threats are evolving rapidly, while resources—financial, human, and technological—remain limited. No single organisation can manage cybersecurity on its own. National resilience therefore depends on collaboration, trust, and the ability to translate knowledge into operational capability.

This white paper focuses on:

- identifying what works well in the Slovenian system,
- analysing key challenges and structural gaps, and
- outlining actionable directions for improvement.

The analysis is structured around thematic areas rather than the original case study structure. It aims to provide clear, forward-looking insights that can support policy development and practical action.

Introduction

Slovenia has built a comprehensive cybersecurity framework over the past decade. The legal and institutional environment is well aligned with EU standards, including the implementation of the NIS2 Directive and other regulatory instruments. Key institutions—such as URSIV (Government Information Security Office)¹, SI-CERT (Slovenian Computer Emergency Response Team)², NCC-SI (National Coordination Centre for Cybersecurity)³, SIGOV-CERT (Governmental CERT)⁴ and industry—provide a functioning structure for cybersecurity lifecycle implementation.

This foundation represents a clear strength. It enables:

- integration into European and international cybersecurity networks,
- participation in joint exercises and research programmes, and
- the establishment of basic mechanisms for national resilience.

However, the impact of this framework is limited by weak implementation. The national cybersecurity strategy has not been updated since 2016 and no longer reflects current threats or technological developments. It lacks clear objectives, defined responsibilities, and measurable outcomes.

As a result, many activities remain at a declarative level. Policies exist, but they are not consistently translated into operational practice. This creates a gap between formal capability and real-world effectiveness.

A key insight is that Slovenia does not lack structures—it lacks alignment and execution. Without a clear strategic direction and accountability, even well-designed frameworks cannot deliver full value needed to respond to sophisticated and AI-enabled growing threats.

This white paper is based on the Slovenian national case study⁵ developed within the COcyber project and builds on its findings to provide a synthesised, policy-oriented perspective.

1 Fragmentation as a systemic barrier

One of the most consistent findings across the case study is fragmentation. This affects governance, cooperation, funding, and operational processes.

¹ URSIV: <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/government-offices/government-information-security-office/>

² SI-CERT: <https://www.cert.si/>

³ NCC-SI: https://cybersecurity-centre.europa.eu/ncc-slovenia_en

⁴ SIGOV-CERT: <https://www.gov.si/en/state-authorities/government-offices/government-information-security-office/about-the-office/sigov-cert-division/>

⁵ COcyber Slovenian case study: [Slovenian case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer](#)

Responsibilities are dispersed across multiple institutions, with limited coordination and unclear leadership. Cooperation often takes place on an ad hoc basis rather than through stable, long-term mechanisms.

This fragmentation leads to several consequences, including duplication of efforts, inefficient use of resources, inconsistent communication, and reduced overall system effectiveness. For example, stakeholders reported that cooperation often depends on informal contacts and short-term projects rather than on permanent coordination structures.

At the strategic level, coordination mechanisms exist, such as regular meetings of representatives of state authorities led by URSIV. However, these do not fully extend to operational collaboration or to systematic involvement of industry and academia.

At the operational level, cooperation is often informal and reactive. Stakeholders collaborate effectively during incidents, but less so in prevention, planning, or capability development.

This pattern highlights a deeper issue: the absence of a unified national approach. Stakeholders repeatedly pointed to fragmented responsibilities, inconsistent coordination, and cooperation that often depends on short-term projects or informal networks. Without a shared vision, strategy and structured coordination, the system remains a collection of capable but disconnected parts.

Recommendation: Strengthen national coordination and structured collaboration

Slovenia should align stakeholders, reduce overlaps, and ensure consistent implementation of cybersecurity priorities across sectors by establishing systematic frameworks for continuous cooperation between government, industry, and academia based on measurable objectives of the national cybersecurity strategy and implementation program. This would replace ad hoc interactions with stable mechanisms for planning, information exchange, and joint capability development.

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2 Critical skills and resource gaps

A major constraint across all areas of the cybersecurity ecosystem is the shortage of skilled professionals. This includes both technical experts and strategic leaders capable of managing complex cybersecurity systems.

The skills gap is reinforced by:

- Limited education and training capacity.
- Low awareness of cybersecurity careers.
- The demand for cybersecurity skills is growing faster than the supply of qualified professionals. The CyberHubs project identified Cybersecurity Implementer/Expert, (Chief) Information Security Officer/Manager, Incident Responder, and Penetration Tester as the most needed roles in Slovenia.

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⁶ Slovenian CyberHub needs analysis: <https://cyberhubs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Slovenia-Cybersecurity-skills-needs-analysis-report.pdf>

- Migration of experts to international markets.

Importantly, the challenge is not only quantitative but also structural. Slovenia lacks a coordinated approach to responsive workforce development that connects education, industry, and public administration.

In parallel, funding remains insufficient and unstable, with many activities still relying on short-term project-based financing rather than predictable long-term support mechanisms. This is reflected more broadly in Slovenia's innovation ecosystem, where the availability of venture capital remains among the lowest in the EU and public investment in R&D remains below the EU average⁷, limiting the transition from research and innovation into market and operational application. National investment is lagging behind and cybersecurity is not consistently prioritised at the political level.

These constraints create a reactive system:

- insufficient investment results in limited workforce capacity and lagging behind in technological development,
- skills shortages and limited resources force organisations to prioritise immediate operational needs, leaving less capacity for long-term workforce and capability development,
- innovation is limited by lack of resources, and
- strategic initiatives remain underdeveloped.

The combined effect of skills shortages and funding limitations significantly reduces the system's ability to evolve and adapt.

Recommendation: Ensure long-term investment in cybersecurity skills and capacity

Slovenia should establish a comprehensive approach to workforce development that connects education, industry, and public administration, with clear career pathways, training programmes, and measures to attract and retain talents. This must be supported by long-term, predictable funding for skills, infrastructure, and innovation, enabling a shift from reactive measures to strategic capacity building. However, successful implementation will depend on long-term political commitment and coordinated action across sectors.

Recommendation: Strengthen investment and support for industry participation in R&D and innovation

Targeted funding and systemic support mechanisms are needed to enable companies—especially SMEs—to actively participate in R&D projects, from early research stages to application. This includes reducing administrative barriers, providing financial incentives, venture capital mechanisms, and ensuring continuity of funding to bridge the gap between research results and operational implementation. However, successful

⁷ European Commission, Country Report Slovenia, 2024: https://economy-finance.ec.europa.eu/economic-surveillance-eu-member-states/country-pages/country-report-slovenia_en

implementation will depend on sustained political and financial support, as well as stronger long-term cooperation between companies, research organisations, and public institutions.

3 Technology transfer: High potential, low maturity

Technology transfer is recognised as a key mechanism for strengthening cybersecurity capabilities. It enables the movement of knowledge and innovation from research to practical application, supporting both national security and economic development.

In Slovenia, however, technology transfer remains underdeveloped and fragmented. The gap between research and market application is particularly pronounced.

Key structural issues include:

- the national strategy does not define research and development goals,
- inadequate national support for innovation processes
- limited incentives and venture capital mechanisms for commercialisation and
- insufficient support for preparation of R&D projects of several partners.
- weak links between universities and industry, stakeholders lack a common understanding of technological autonomy and dual-use cybersecurity.

These challenges have a cumulative impact. The absence of clear strategic direction at the national level weakens coordination and long-term investment planning, while cooperation between academia and industry remains limited and largely project-based. Research organisations are still primarily focused on academic outputs, whereas companies are often fragmented and driven by short-term priorities. As a result, promising research frequently fails to progress into operational use, creating a persistent “valley of death” and contributing to Slovenia’s continued dependence on foreign technologies and limited strategic autonomy.

Despite these challenges, there are positive signals. Participation in EU and NATO programmes, as well as selected R&D projects, demonstrates that effective collaboration is possible when conditions are right.

The key insight is that technology transfer works best when:

- objectives are clearly defined,
- stakeholders are engaged early,
- coordination is strong,
- effective incentive mechanisms are in place to reward knowledge transfer and its practical application.

Scaling these conditions remains a central challenge.

Recommendation: Strengthen strategic coordination of technology transfer

Slovenia should improve the practical functioning of existing mechanisms, such as technology transfer offices and intermediary institutions, by clarifying their roles, increasing their capacity, and making them more proactive in connecting research with industry. However, achieving sustained cooperation may require stronger political commitment, stable funding, and long-term engagement from both research organisations and industry stakeholders.

Recommendation: Create incentives and operational support for commercialisation and collaboration

Effective mechanisms are needed to reward knowledge transfer and support the transition from research to application, including incentives for researchers, stronger industry involvement, and dedicated support for advancing solutions to market readiness. This should be complemented by improved access to venture capital and financing instruments that enable start-ups and companies to scale and implement new cybersecurity solutions.

4 Information sharing: Between formal structures and informal practice

Effective cybersecurity depends on timely and trusted information sharing. Slovenia has established formal mechanisms, including CERT structures, legal reporting obligations, and platforms such as MISP⁸.

These mechanisms provide a solid foundation, particularly at the strategic level. Coordination among public authorities is relatively strong, and incident reporting processes are defined.

However, practical implementation reveals several gaps:

- trust between stakeholders is limited,
- feedback mechanisms are weak,
- sharing of lessons learned and good practices is very limited and
- interoperability between systems is insufficient.

In many cases, the most effective exchanges occur through informal channels—the so-called “phonebook system”—rather than through formal and secured platforms. While this enables rapid response, it creates risks related to transparency, inclusiveness, and sustainability.

Cross-sector information sharing is particularly weak. Barriers include:

- fear of reputational damage,
- legal uncertainty,
- lack of incentives, and
- different levels of organisational maturity.

These barriers reduce timely threat detection, limit coordinated incident response, and weaken collective situational awareness, ultimately affecting overall national cyber resilience.

International cooperation, in contrast, is more developed and often more trusted. Slovenian stakeholders benefit from access to knowledge, best practices, and joint exercises at the European and NATO levels.

The key challenge is to translate these external strengths into a coherent national system. This requires building trust, standardising processes, and creating clear value for participants.

⁸ MISP: <https://www.cert.si/obvezna-priglasitev-incidenta/>

Recommendation: Formalise and standardise national information-sharing mechanisms

Slovenia should move from fragmented and informal practices to a structured system with clear roles, standardised procedures, and interoperable platforms, ensuring consistent and timely exchange of cybersecurity information across all sectors. However, successful implementation will depend on building trust among stakeholders, improving cross-sector coordination, and ensuring active participation from both public and private actors.

Recommendation: Build trust and incentives for cross-sector information sharing

Targeted measures are needed to strengthen trust among stakeholders, including clear rules on data use, feedback mechanisms, and incentives that encourage organisations to share information without fear of reputational or legal risk. However, implementation may require gradual cultural change, stronger institutional support, and sustained efforts to establish transparent and reliable cooperation practices across sectors.

5 Dual-use innovation: A strategic opportunity not yet realised

Dual-use technologies—those applicable in both civilian and defence contexts—represent a major opportunity for Slovenia. They can drive innovation, strengthen resilience, and support participation in European programmes.

The civilian sector is the main source of such innovation, particularly in areas such as cryptography, threat detection, and data analysis.

However, the potential of dual-use technologies is not fully realised. Key barriers include:

- lack of clear national strategy on the cooperation of the civilian and military sectors in the national defence doctrine,
- limited cooperation between civilian and defence sectors,
- regulatory complexity and uncertainty, and
- low awareness among stakeholders.

The defence sector operates under strict security constraints, while the civilian sector lacks understanding of defence requirements. This creates a gap that limits collaboration and slows innovation.

At the same time, export control regulations are well developed, but they focus more on control than on enabling innovation. For example, complex procedures and uncertainty regarding the classification and use of dual-use technologies can discourage cooperation and slow the transition from research to operational application. This imbalance further restricts progress.

Despite these challenges, successful examples—such as joint exercises and selected R&D projects—show that cooperation can deliver strong results.

The key insight is that dual-use innovation requires:

- clear strategic direction,
- structured cooperation mechanisms, and
- alignment between policy, research, and industry.

Recommendation: Strengthen the national framework and cooperation for dual-use cybersecurity innovation

Slovenia should define clear priorities, roles, and procedures for dual-use technologies, while establishing practical mechanisms for cooperation between civilian, defence, and research stakeholders, including joint projects, knowledge exchange, and mutual understanding of requirements, enabling more effective development and application of dual-use solutions. However, successful implementation will depend on

stronger strategic alignment, clearer regulatory guidance, and the ability to build trust and long-term cooperation across sectors.

Conclusions: From fragmentation to systemic integration

Slovenia has established many of the essential building blocks of a modern cybersecurity ecosystem. These include a solid regulatory foundation aligned with EU frameworks, dedicated institutions with defined roles, active participation in international networks, and growing experience in research and operational cooperation.

At the same time, the overall system does not yet function as a coherent whole. Across all areas analysed—governance, skills, technology transfer, information sharing, and dual-use innovation—a similar issue appears: activities exist, but they are not sufficiently connected, coordinated, or translated into long-term impact.

The main challenge is therefore not to build new structures, but to make existing ones work better together. This means moving from fragmented responsibilities and project-based cooperation towards more consistent coordination, clearer roles, and stable mechanisms for collaboration.

For this reason, a practical starting point in the short term is to address fragmentation by **strengthening regular communication and structured cooperation between stakeholders**. This should include continuous exchanges between government, industry, academia, and the research community to identify what works well, where gaps remain, and how future activities and priorities should be adjusted based on operational experience and evolving needs.

In the medium term, **stronger cooperation frameworks, more predictable support mechanisms, and better aligned incentives** will be needed to support knowledge exchange, joint capability development, and the practical application of research and innovation.

Some of the broader enabling conditions, however, will require a longer-term effort. **Cybersecurity needs to be recognised as a strategic national priority, supported by sustained political commitment and stable investment**. Achieving this will require continuous dialogue, long-term policy alignment, and broad stakeholder engagement. The preparation of the new national cybersecurity strategy and accompanying action plan provides an important opportunity to strengthen this recognition and establish a more coordinated long-term approach.

Slovenia should continue building on its existing strengths, particularly its **active participation in European and Euro-Atlantic initiatives**. These provide access to knowledge, funding, partnerships, and operational experience, and should now be more systematically transferred and expanded across the broader national cybersecurity ecosystem. In the short to medium term, this can serve as a catalyst for stronger internal coordination and capability development.

It is difficult to establish strict priorities, as the identified challenges are closely interconnected. Weak coordination in one area directly affects progress in others, including information sharing, technology transfer, skills development, and innovation capacity. In addition, the lack of stronger national support and

strategic direction means that many activities still depend on individual initiatives and immediate operational needs, limiting broader systemic progress.

Cybersecurity is a field where effectiveness depends on cooperation. Individual capabilities are important, but resilience is achieved only when they are connected into a well-functioning system.

For Slovenia, moving from fragmentation to systemic integration is therefore a practical priority. With better coordination, clearer direction, and sustained cooperation, the existing foundations can be translated into a more effective and resilient cybersecurity ecosystem.

This white paper is based on the COcyber Slovenian Case Study⁹, which provides a more detailed analysis of the identified challenges, stakeholder perspectives, and recommendations.

⁹ COcyber Slovenian case study: [Slovenian case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer](#)